

The Land Division Court records – geographical distribution of court cases

Ari Vesalainen

1. Introduction

Digitization has revolutionized history research. The digital world is evolving at an ever-increasing pace, and the new tools and methods it is bringing are useful in historical research also. At the turn of the millennium, studying historical materials always required visiting an archive or a library. With the latest development in digitization, online archives make it easier to find the correct information and speed up the search for information. Furthermore, everyone who wants can access this digitized data from their home computer, regardless of time and place.

Although, even if the materials are more readily available, one challenge remains: interpreting the old, often handwritten texts. Traditionally this has always required close reading. It is time-consuming, and addressing large complex materials is very difficult.

With new Machine Learning (ML) technologies, recognizing handwritten text has taken significant steps forward over the past few years. For example, the Transkribus software platform, developed as part of the EU's READ (Recognition and Enrichment of Archival Documents) project, enables the automatic recognition of various handwritten texts [1].

The primary purpose of this project is to build a complete end-to-end pipeline to process digitized historical documents using handwritten text recognition and analyze if the outcome is suitable for further text analysis. The data in this project consists of land division court records from the 19th-century. Picture 1 shows the extraction of the digitized court record and related transcribed text.

År 1846. den 3de September sammantröd de Äyödelmins Rätten å Hemmanet No 5. i Jäniksälä by och Mändyharju socken af Heinola Härad kos Bonden Christer Pekkola: När varande Härvid Ordförenden Herr vice Häradshöfdingen Johan Wilhelm Neygren samt Ledamuten Märten Mårtensson Hyyryläin från Myntilä.

Picture 1. Extract from a court case with transcribed text.

Chapter 2 describes the research questions the project aims to resolve. Chapter 3 talks about data and the steps required to use it. Chapter 4 describes the methods used for data mining to extract relevant information for the research questions. Finally, chapter 5 provides answers to the research questions, and chapter 6 includes a discussion and conclusions of the project.

2. Humanities research questions

The Land Division Court (Finnish: maanjako-oikeus, Swedish: ägodelningsrätten) was a special court that examined and settled disputes and appeals arising out of land ownership. These courts were operational between 1775–1972. The Land Division Court in the Mikkeli province was an ad hoc

court composed of a chairman, two reputable members, and a scribe. The landowners elected both the chairman and the court members [5].

The data used in this project consists of the Land Division Court records in Mikkeli province between 1830 and 1874. Scribes recorded court sessions first to concept documents, and later these were transcribed to be further submitted to a court of appeals (Finnish: hovioikeus, Swedish: hovrätt) for checking and archiving. The actual documents are in the National Archive of Finland.

To test and analyze the robustness of the pipeline, we have defined some specific research questions.

- Identify individual court cases and study the distribution of the cases between parishes. What is the geographical distribution of the cases? Does the distribution change during the measured period?
- Identify the persons and their home location involved in court cases?

The

3. Data and data formats

The dataset used for this project consists of 6143 JPEG images of the land division court records from Mikkeli province from 1830 to 1874. Each image has two pages. These pages represent 782 different court cases.

Picture 2. Typical double-page image of the court record.

The court records have been digitized during 2016 by Finland's Family History Association (FFHA) and are currently available to members of FFHA. FFHA digitized the material as a crowdsourcing project using professional camera systems to ensure good image quality. During 2020 images were uploaded to the READ Coop server and run through the handwritten text recognition (HTR) process.

The National Archive of Finland coordinated the creation of the HTR model during 2018-2019 as a crowdsourcing project. The training material is a subset of the Renovated District Court Records (Finnish: Kihlakunnanoikeuksien renovoidut tuomiokirjat, Swedish: Häradsrätternas renoverade

domböcker). It covers almost 3000 double-page images from 1809-1870, representing nearly 60 different court districts. Most of the text is in Swedish. The reported model character error (CER) rate is 6.4% for the training set and 4.2% for the validation set [6].

The transcribed text is stored in the READ Coop server as an XML file and downloaded to the computer for further processing using Transkribus REST API [3]. Some metadata is also combined with the text to link text and original images during the download process.

Picture 3 describes the typical phases of the project which utilize Transkribus or other text recognition methods [1]. Raw material covers the materials in archives or libraries; materials can be historical documents and printed books. Therefore, the processing always starts with digitization: materials are scanned or photographed and stored in JPEG or another digital format. During the preprocessing phase, the system transforms image files to a uniform format and improves the quality of images for the remaining steps. Pre-processing can include image deskewing, normalization, noise reduction, and binarization.

Picture 3. Phases of projects utilizing Transkribus

Text recognition covers two main steps: segmentation and recognition. The idea of segmentation is to break the whole image into subparts (e.g., text regions, paragraphs, and text lines) which can be processed further. Actual character and word recognition happen in the recognition phase. The system identifies the characters during this phase, and an XML file is created, including a link between the original JPEG file and recognized text. Modern HTR or optical character recognition (OCR) systems use Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to achieve the required accuracy.

The researcher prepares the text material for the actual research during the post-processing phase. Depending on the research questions, a researcher can use different techniques. For example, the phase can include steps to improve OCR accuracy by comparing detected words against a given dictionary to detect interpretation errors. The data analysis & research phase uses data mining and other techniques to extrapolate patterns and new knowledge from the existing data.

In this project the focus is on the data analysis & research phase. Earlier phases are well documented in Transkribus documentation and can be used as such.

4. Data analysis and research methods

The data analysis & research phase can be further split into subtasks. Picture 4 shows the subtask used in this project.

Picture 4. Research and Data analysis pipeline for the project.

Download data and transform the text

Transkribus uses XML to store transcribed text. Picture 5 shows a typical representation of one line in the original digital image. Coords points and baseline points define a polygon that locates the actual text inside the image, and TextEquiv shows the interpretation in plain text.

```
<TextLine id="r1116" custom="readingOrder {index:15;}">
  <Coords points="162,1194 1005,1168 1456,1214 1722,1194 1723,1143 162,1131"/>
  <Baseline points="171,1172 248,1170 325,1170 402,1169 479,1169 556,1167 633,1167 710,1166
787,1166 864,1164 942,1164 1019,1164 1096,1164 1173,1166 1250,1166 1327,1167 1404,1169
1481,1172 1558,1174 1635,1178 1713,1181"/>
  <TextEquiv>
  <Unicode>Karlilä, Savila, Walkala och Karwila byamäns</Unicode>
</TextEquiv>
</TextLine>
```

Picture 5. Baseline representation in XML file.

The user can manipulate XML files by accessing them through Transkribus REST API, parsing the file using some XML library, and extracting the text [3].

Natural Language Processing

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a technique to extract information from text documents. The methods used in this project are tokenization, named entity recognition, and N-grams.

Word and sentence tokenization are methods to separate the continuous text into words or sentences. Word tokenization works well in Swedish text. The biggest challenge arose as the automatic character recognition lost some of the word boundaries, and in many cases, the word split is arbitrary. Sentence tokenization worked very poorly as the text does not follow the modern grammatical rules, and, here, the automatic recognition caused problems as the sentence boundaries were not clear.

Named Entity Recognition (NER). The initial idea for data mining was to use the NER method. A researcher can use NER to extract named entities (e.g., person names, locations, and temporal entities) from the unstructured data. As the text is old Swedish, I decided to test the Swedish BERT model. Although the model is based on Wikipedia articles, I hoped it could work here. Unfortunately, the results were somewhat mixed: for person names, it worked pretty well, and it was able to detect typical Swedish person names, but for location names, its performance was low, and I decided to use it only for the person names.

N-grams

N-gram is a contiguous sequence of n items where the item can be a word or character. I used Bigrams and Trigrams in this project (i.e., n is 2 or 3). I decided to use this approach as many vital terms follow a specific pattern in the text. For example, the word "socken" often follows the parish's name, i.e., "Mäntyharju socken" refers to a parish called Mäntyharju. Therefore, searching for these bigrams will help detect all parishes in the text. Similarly, houses are identified by using a pattern "hemmanet" "no" <number of the house>, i.e., trigrams with two first words fixed, which helps to

identify the place. Usage of n-grams calls word tokenization, where it separates the text into a list of words, and then searching for the sequence help to identify the n-gram item in question.

Normalization of names

During the normalization, the data cleaning process converts identified names into standard names, e.g., Mäntyharju is a standard form for Mändyharju and Menduharju. The normalization is essential as it removes the redundant terms and cleans the data. This step is critical as the text is automatically recognized. For example, although the CER is about than 5%, which is considered good, the reality is quite the opposite. The poor accuracy is visible in parish names (e.g., there is more than 100 different ways how Mäntyharju have been transcribed, and Kangasniemi and Rantasalmi more than in 50 different ways). Similar, although the more minor, challenge was detected how the month in dates was recognized.

These normalization challenges were resolved by creating two simple supervised learning classifiers. The training data was collected from the actual data, annotated manually. A similar technique could be used efficiently for other similar normalization tasks.

Visualization

Visualization is a technique to use graphics or diagrams to communicate and deliver the message related to the topic we want to explain. In this project, we utilize visualization to easily present the analysis results.

4.1. Data analysis tools

Picture 6 shows a typical workflow. `trdownload.py` extracts text from XML files in Transkribus server and stores in Folder 1. `CompLit-Data_Manipulation.py` with `separate`-option processes these files further and stores the separated court cases as text files to Folder 2. `CompLit-Data_Manipulation.py` with the `extract`-option process each court cases text file and extracts related data to another text file that is stored in Folder 3.

Picture 6. Pipeline of programs

The programming part of the project covers three utilities:

- `trdownload.py` extracts and downloads text data from the Transkribus server,
- `CompLit-Data_Manipulation.py` separates different court cases are into individual text files to be processed further, detects bigrams and trigrams enabling to identify critical terms from the data and detect NER entities (e.g., person names) in the text.
- `CompLit-Visualization.ipynb` visualizes the data by drawing histograms of court cases over the given period and geographical map of the cases over the Mikkeli province.

All programs are stored in the zenodo.org.

trdownload.py

Usage:

```
trdownload.py [-h] [--download] [--password PASSWORD] [--username USERNAME] [--docfile  
DOCFILE] [--doc DOC] [--output OUTFILE] [--dir DIRECTORY] [--list]
```

Download transcribed text from Transkribus server

optional arguments:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit  
--download          Download requested documents from the Transkribus server  
--password PASSWORD Password for the Transkribus server  
--username USERNAME Username for the Transkribus server  
--docfile DOCFILE  File of document names you want to be separated  
--doc DOC           Document to be separated  
--output OUTFILE   File where the transcribed text will be stored  
--dir DIRECTORY    Directory where the transcribed texts will be stored  
--list             List documents stored in Transkribus server
```

ComplIt-Data_Manipulation.py

Usage:

```
ComplIt-Data_manipulation.py [-h] [--separate] [--docfile DOCFILE] [--doc DOC] [--indir INDIR]  
[--outdir OUTDIR] [--extract] [THRESH] [--action SEARCHSTR] [--suffix SUFFIX] [--threshold  
THRESH] [--config CONFIG]
```

Land division court cases - text search

optional arguments:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit  
--separate          Extract individual court cases into separate text file  
--docfile DOCFILE  File of document names you want to be separated  
--doc DOC           Document to be separated  
--indir INDIR      Directory for input files  
--outdir OUTDIR    Directory for output files  
--extract          Explore given court cases and search for text patterns  
--action SEARCHSTR Search action to be done  
--suffix SUFFIX    File name suffix for search data metadata files  
--threshold THRESH Threshold value for NER detection  
--config CONFIG    Directory for configuration files
```

ComplIt-Visualization.ipynb

Python program in Jupyter notebook that is used to visualize the results. The functions included

- Draw histograms of court cases over the years 1830-1874.
- Draw a map that shows the distribution of court cases geographically over the Mikkeli province.
- Draw a word cloud that visually shows the frequencies of parishes over the Mikkeli province.

The following example show how the programs can be used. The first command connects to Transkribus server and downloads and extracts transcribed data for documents listed in download.txt. The text is extracted into text file and stored in "C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/trdocs/" directory. The second command takes the text files and separates these into text files where each individual court case is in its own file. The third command goes through all court case files and extracts the starting date of the case. The extracted data is stored for each court case individually in the "C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/metadata2/" directory.

```
python trdownload.py --username "username@domain.fi" --password secret --download -  
-docfile download.txt --dir "C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/trdocs/"
```

```
python CompLit-Data_manipulation.py --separate --docfile download.txt --indir  
"C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/trdocs/" --outdir  
"C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/cases2/"
```

```
python CompLit-Data_manipulation.py --extract --docfile download.txt --indir  
"C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/cases2/" --outdir  
"C:/Data/Programming/transkribus/metadata2/" --action "pdate" --suffix "CASE"
```

All programming uses Python, and table 1 lists the main libraries used for the project.

Library	Purpose
NumPy	Data manipulation
Pandas	Data manipulation and visualization
sklearn	Machine Learning
folium	Data visualization
matplotlib	Data visualization
nltk	Natural Language Processing
transformers	Natural Language Processing

Table 1. Python libraries in the project.

5. Answers to research questions

As mentioned at the beginning of this report, the research questions focus on two main areas:

1. Identifying parishes and how the court cases are distributed
2. Are we able to identify person names from the text?

The following two sections provides answers to these questions.

5.1. Parish geographical distribution and changes over time

As mentioned earlier, the analysis identified 782 court cases. Parish was automatically detected for 769 cases, and only for 24 cases, it failed. Similarly, the year was detected for 767 cases, and in 15 cases, the method failed. Picture 6 shows the yearly distribution of the cases. The peak of cases happened in the 1850s when almost 40 cases per year were handled. The same kind of development can also be seen for Mikkeli and Mäntyharju at the parish level.

Picture 6. Yearly frequencies of court cases between 1830 and 1880.

All parishes are in the data. However, the court cases are not evenly spread over the parishes. The top 6 parishes (Mikkeli 138, Kangasniemi 100, Mäntyharju 100, Juva 87, Pieksämäki 72 and Ristiina 48) are representing almost 70% of the cases. Rest, seven parishes represent about 26% of the cases. Also, some parishes that are not part of Mikkeli province although identified.

Picture 7. Parishes with most of the court cases.

Pictures 7 and 8 give more details to check if any differences can be seen between parishes. As the number of cases is relatively low and the period is rather long, we must be cautious in making conclusions. However, based on pictures 7 and 8, the timing is not the same for all parishes. For example, the most active period in Juva and Kangasniemi is happening earlier than in Mikkeli and Mäntyharju. Is this happening by accident, or is there an apparent reason? This would require some further study.

Picture 7. Histogram of top 6 parishes.

Picture 8 shows how the cases are spread over the geographical area of Mikkeli province. The size of the circle indicates the relative number of cases. One observation is that it looks that relatively more cases have happened on the west side of the given area. However, this observation has not been studied further.

Picture 8. Geographical distribution of cases.

Picture 9 is an example of how the visualization can be used to highlight the findings. The picture highlights the difference seen by the top 6 and rest of the parishes.

Picture 9. Word cloud illustrating the case frequency.

Overall, the pictures and statistics prove we could extract meaningful data to answer the research question satisfactorily.

5.2. Persons involved in court cases

Identifying person names requires a different solution as there is no typical pattern to detect personal names. Therefore, we will use NER technique for this. The implementation uses Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) -model developed by The Swedish Public Employment Service [2]. For example, NER detection is applied for the text in picture 1, and the output is shown. As the picture 10 shows, the program detects "Christer Pekkola" and "Johan Wilhelm Neygren". The nlp function returns the list of detected NERs. However, the tokenizer BERT splits words into multiple tokens, and an additional function was written to combine sequential NERs with the same type and presents this as one entity. Score defines the confidence index for the NER; if it is less, that specific threshold program ignores it.

```
{'entity': 'PER',
  'score': 0.9996406,
  'index': 46,
  'word': 'Christer Pekkola',
  'start': 141,
  'end': 157},
{'entity': 'PER',
  'score': 0.9997706,
  'index': 65,
  'word': 'Johan Wilhelm Neygren',
  'start': 215,
  'end': 236}]
```

Picture 10. Example of Swedish BERT model output.

When the whole dataset was searched, the program was able to identify 87216 personal names representing 37074 different names. Table 2 shows the most frequent names found from the dataset. All these names are valid. About 63% of the names occur only once and 23.5% twice. About 10% of names are found four or more times.

Name	#instances
'Johan'	570
'Anders'	516
'Matts'	472

'Petter'	436
'Michel'	333
'von Becker'	278
'Herman Grotenfelt'	249
'Adam'	240
'Thomas'	230
'Ehnberg'	200

Table 2. The most frequent names in the dataset.

Further analysis shows that due to the HTR accuracy, the quality is questionable:

- Character recognition errors can cause that same name can have several different forms. For example, Nikkinen can be shown as Likkinen, Pikkinen, Vikkinen, Wikkinen, Hikkinen, or in some other forms. NER detection identifies all these forms; however, name normalization would be required to use these effectively.
- In some cases, the word boundary is not correct and this leads to wrong interpretations of names: name is split (e.g., Chri ster Christersson Niroids, or Henrik Gabriel Sa venius) or two or more names are combined (e.g., Christer Pålsson PiiraMatts Mattsson Wesalainen, or Adam Christersson Peckola Magnus KarhuChristen Leppä). In some cases nlp interprets other words than names as names (e.g., Enkan Anna Johansdotter Urtikainen).

Nlp function restricts the size of the searched text. To overcome this, I planned to split the text into sentences. However, as explained earlier, it did not work correctly due to difficulties identifying correct sentence boundaries. So, I broke the text into 512-character chunks as a workaround, which helped. However, as a side effect, it introduced another error source as this might also lead to a misplaced word boundary. How this would resolve is left for future tasks.

NLP and NER detection work very well, and even it is developed for modern Swedish, it can also detect old names as these have changed only marginally [2]. Appendix 1 and 2 give examples of how this has worked. Some errors were detected during the tests, but these were mainly due to the interpretation errors in character recognition. Another source of errors is the misplaced word boundaries.

The results show that NLP techniques could be used also in this context. The modern NER models are robust enough to extract meaningful information out of the used text. The approach is not error-free, and results should be treated cautiously. However, usage in this context would require further work to understand better the source of errors and how these could be avoided.

6. Discussion and conclusions

The primary purpose of this project is to build a complete end-to-end pipeline to process digitized historical documents using handwritten text recognition and analyze if the outcome is suitable for further text analysis. The results confirm that this can be done, and the programs created are flexible enough to be used as the base for future similar projects.

Although the process works, there are several reasons why the process should be used with caution, and it is impossible to draw general conclusions from the material.

The Mikkeli province was founded in 1831, and it initially included 13 parishes. During the years of 1831-1880, some parishes were divided into smaller parishes, and at the end of the period, the number of parishes was a little bit more. Also, in 1831, some parishes were divided between two provinces. When we analyze the statistics in detail, we notice that less than half of the parishes

cover almost 70% of the court cases. The rest seven parishes cover only 26%, and a minor portion of parishes are outside Mikkeli province or unknown. As the court cases are not evenly spread, there is a question about why. One reason may be that the court cases could be found from another province's records as some parishes were divided between two regions. Another reason could be because of timing, these court cases were linked to land reform (e.g., enclosure movement), and this could have been done at different times in different parishes [4]. Also, it is not known how often the disputes and appeals were processed outside court. Some of the court records could have been destroyed as well. This question should be studied further.

All materials are written in old Swedish, and some of the tools are not working well in this context. NER works well with person names as the names in 19th century Finland are very similar to those in Sweden today. However, some names were truncated in some cases as some characters were dropped. On the other hand, NER does not work with location names as the Finnish location names are different from Swedish ones. Furthermore, the spelling of words was not yet standardized during the 19th century. The same word could have many various spelling forms, making the interpretation of words more difficult. It is also vital to remember the texts have been processed several times, names of locations or persons may have changed incorrectly, leading to wrong assumptions.

The material covers 782 court cases, and on the average length of the court case is 16 pages (8 double pages). However, the variation is significant as the shortest cases cover only two pages, and the longest one is 268 pages. Also, the shortest case deals with only one village and one house when the longest cases deal with tens of houses in tens of villages. In practice, this means that the content for cases is also probably very different.

The HTR model was originally built to interpret 19th century court cases, and as such, the dataset used is ideal. However, the model's accuracy raises some questions as the interpretation of some names is almost random (e.g., more than 100 interpretations for Mäntyharju). This inaccuracy puts some pressure on the normalization and cleaning of the data. This project addressed this by using a simple machine learning classifier to normalize parish names. This solution will also work if the program is used in another context. However, then the classifier needs to be manually updated accordingly. Another approach would be to improve the HTR model and provide more training data to improve the accuracy and generality.

This project uses archived court records that are transcribed records based on original concept documents. It is impossible to know how the transcription matches the initial session in the court. This might impact results as we do not know if there have been general instructions.

Using old historical court cases in research is problematic since the data could be highly biased, and it is not possible to make too general assumptions based on the material. However, as the project's primary purpose is to test the technical feasibility of the approach, and the selected research questions are such, the bias is not a significant problem. Therefore, the findings are based on data explored from the existing materials, and no general conclusions are drawn.

The programs developed in this project are generic and could be used to address similar research questions. However, if I would have had more time, there are a few topics I would like to improve:

- Data manipulation code should be re-written to be more compact and robust to process more generic data searches for the text.
- Trdownload.py should be extended to record more metadata elements to ensure a more generic approach.
- Error handling and error recovery should be enhanced.

Overall, I am very satisfied with the results. These proves that even with some limitations text generated by Transkribus can be used for further analysis and research. As the accuracy is still questionable and depends heavily on material used, special attention should be put on data cleaning and data post-processing.

References

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[4]	Petri Talvitie. Kyläosuudesta yksityiseen maanomistukseen. Isojako Länsi-Uudellamaalla 1700-luvulla. Historiallisia tutkimuksia Helsingin yliopistosta XXVIII. University of Helsinki. 2012.
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Appendices

Appendix 1

<p>År 1856 den 1 Juli sammanträdde Ägodilnings Rätten i Mändyharji Socken och Heinola Härad af 5. Michels Län å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by hos Bonden Adam Lepistö. Närvarande härvid ordföranden Herr vill Häradshöfdingen Johan Wilhelm Fggrén jemte Ledamöterna Rusthållaren Johan Mynttinen och Bonden Mårten Hyynyläinen, begge från Mynttilä by. Protocollat fördes af undertecknad Herman Liikanen som i egen namn af Bondens biträde Ägodilnings Rätten. Efter det Bonden Anders Mattsson Nikkinen, såsom ägare af 15 uti halfva eller 1/6 del utaf hela Hemmanet No 8 i Toivolaby, under den 22 Oktober 1855. hos Herr Gouverneuren i Länet uti då ingifven skrift, anmält missnöje öfver den skiftes utstakning och odlings m. m. Liqid, som Herr vice Landtmätaren Henrik Gabriel Savinius, medelst lenier uppgått å marken, den 10. September berörde ån emellan Anders Mårtensson Nikkinens 1/6, å ena samt Bonden Adam Lepistos ägande 1/3 del i hela hemmanet å andra sidan; som alla redan härförinnan, genom behörigt skifte, blifvit afskild frånandra hälften i samma hemman, och hvaröfver besväranden vidfogadt berörde dess missnöjes anmälan det af bemälda Herr Landtmälare öfver skiftes utstakningen uti händigade bevis så lydande</p> <p>Under nedanstående dag är skiftes utstakningen vidfogad m. m. Liqid emellan delägarene å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by af Mändyharji Socken fulländad, samt jordägarene förständigade: att i händelse af missnöje dermed, sådant, med bifogande af detta bevis, hos Herr Gouverneuren öfverlämnat inom Sex veckor, häröfver denna dag dock oberäknad, skriftligen tillkännagifva, Förrättningsstället i Soivola by, den 10 September 1855</p> <p>Herr Gabr. Savenius.</p> <p>Ja har Herr Gouverneuren uti högtvördad Resolution af den 24. Oktober 1855. Remitterat besvärs skriften till ordföranden i Ägodilnings Rätten, i det afseende 58. §. i Kejsarliga Reglemenlet, den 15 Maji 1848 förmår, hvarefter, sedan besvärs skriften under den 25 April 1856.</p>	<p>År 1856. den 1 Juli sammanträdde Ägodilnings Rätten i Mändyharji Socken och Heinola Härad af 5. Michels Län å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by hos Bonden Adam Lepistö- Närvarande härvid ordföranden Herr vill Häradshöfdingen Johan Wilhelm Fggrén jemte Ledamöterna Rusthållaren Johan Mynttinen och Bonden Mårten Hyynyläinen, begge från Mynttilä by. Protocollet fördes af undertecknad Herman Liikanen som i egenskap af Secreterare biträde Ägodilnings Rätten. Efter det Bonden Anders Mattsson Nikkinen, såsom ägare af 15 uti halfva eller 1/6 del utaf hela Hemmanet No 8 i Toivolaby, under den 22 Oktober 1855. hos Herr Gouverneuren i Länet- uti då ingifven skrift, anmält missnöje öfver den skiftes utstakning och odlings m. m. Liqid, som Herr vice Landtmätaren Henrik Gabriel Savinius, medelst lenier uppgått å marken, den 10. September berörde ån emellan Anders Mårtensson Nikkinens 1/6, å ena samt Bonden Adam Lepistos ägande 1/3 del i hela hemmanet å andra sidan; som alla redan härförinnan, genom behörigt skifte, blifvit afskild frånandra hälften i samma hemman, och hvaröfver besväranden vidfogadt berörde dess missnöjes anmälan det af bemälda Herr Landtmälare öfver skiftes utstakningen uti händigade bevis så lydande</p> <p>Under nedanstående dag är skiftes utstakningen och odlings m. m. Liqid emellan delägarene å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by och Mändykarju Socken fulländad, samt jordägarene förständigade: att i händelse af missnöje dermed, sådant, med bifogande af detta bevis, hos Herr Gouverneuren öfverlämnat inom Sex veckor; hvarefter denna dag dock oberäknad vilkpte intyges skriftligen tillkännagifva, Förrättningsstället i Soivola by, den 10 September 1855</p> <p>Henr Gabr. Tavenius</p> <p>så har Herr Gouverneuren uti högtvördad resolution af den 24. Oktober 1855. Remitterat besvärs skriften till ordföranden i Ägodilnings Rätten, i det afseende 58. SS. i Kejsarliga Reglemenlet, den 15 Maji 1848 förmår, hvarefter, sedan besvärs skriften under den 25 April 1856.</p>
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The personal name NERs identified are:

Adam Lepistö	Correct
Johan Wilhelm Fggrén	Incorrectly transcribed surname, correct surname is Nygren
Johan Mynttinen	Correct
Mårten Hyynyläinen	Incorrectly transcribed, correct format is Mårten Hyryläinen
Herman Liikanen	Correct
Anders Mattsson Nikkinen	Correct
Henrik Gabriel Savinius	Incorrectly transcribed as Savenius is transcribed as Savinius
Anders Mårtensson Nikkinens	Correct
Adam Lepisto	Incorrectly transcribed as ö is recognized as o
Tavenius	Misses two first names and surname is transcribed incorrectly, correct Henr. Gabr: Savenius

Appendix 2

<p>År 1855. den 20. Juni sammanträdde Söpdelnings Rätten å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by af Händyvärg socken, hos ägaren af två tredjedelar deri Bonden Adam Lepistö; Därvarande härvid Ordföranden, Herr vice Häradshöfdingen Johan Wilhelm Typén samt Ordinarie Ledamöterna, Bönderne Johan Thomasson Hynttinen, från Hynttilä, och Mårten Hårtersson Hyypysäinen, från Hyrylä by.</p> <p>Protokollet fördes af Hof Rätts extra kapliten Julius Typén för tillfället antagen Sekreterare i Rätten.</p> <p>Sedan Herr vice kändsmätaren Henrik Gabriel Savenius under den 1. November nästlidne är, tillfäst Herr käre kändsmätaren ett följande:</p> <p>”Ödmjukaste Memorial:</p> <p>Vid den klyfnings beredning jag under nedanstående dag, förskrift å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by af Händyvärg socken, emellan Bonden Adam Sigfridsson Kepistö, å ena, och Bonden Anders Mattsson Nikkinen, å andra sidan, på förklarade sig den följande intressenten Sdam Kepistö obeläten med det förslag om bohlstade utflyttningen, som förrättningsmännen afgifvit; på får hos Herr Sfdé käre kändsmätaren jag ödmjukast anhålla, om denna höfghet anmälande till Händyvärg Sockens bydelnings Rätts upptagande och afdömande. Händyvärg, den 1. November 1854.</p> <p>Herr Gabr. Savenius.</p> <p>Så har Herr Sfdé käre kändsmätaren H. J. ärnefult på har Herr käre kändsmätaren öfverlemnadt afsvinnat Memorial till Herr Grevernöraren i Länet, som sedermera remitterat ären- gäll.</p>	<p>År 1855. den 20. Juni sammanträdde Söpdelnings Rätten å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by af Händyvärg socken, hos ägaren af två tredjedelar deri Bonden Adam Lepistö; Närvarande härvid Ordföranden, Herr vice Häradshöfdingen Johan Wilhelm Typén samt Ordinarie Ledamöterna, Bönderne Johan Thomasson Hynttinen, från Hynttilä, och Mårten Hårtersson Hyypysäinen, från Hyrylä by.</p> <p>Protokollet fördes af Hof Rätts extra kapliten Julius Typén för tillfället antagen Sekreterare i Rätten</p> <p>Sedan Herr vice kändsmätaren Henrik Gabriel Savenius under den 1. November nästlidne är, tillsandt Herr käre kändsmätaren ett följande:</p> <p>Ödmjukaste Hemmal.</p> <p>Vid den klyfnings beredning jag under nedanstående dag förehäft å halfva skatte hemmanet No 8. i Toivola by af Klandparja soken, emellan Bonden Adam Sigfridsson Kepistö, å enä, och Bonden Anders Mattsson Nikkinen, å andra sidan, så förklarade sig den sistnämnde intressenten Sdam Kepistö obeläten med det förslag om bohlstade utflyttningen, som förrättningsmännen afgifvit; så får hos Herr Sfdé käre kändsmätaren jag ödmjukast anhålla om denna tvistighets anmälande till Händyvärg Sockens bydelnings Rätts upptagande och afdömande. Mändyhärgi, den 1. November 1854.</p> <p>Henr. Gab. Savenius.</p> <p>N: 13.</p> <p>Till Herr Ffdr käne Landtmätaren H. J. ärnefult. sa har Herr Läne Landtmätaren öfverlemnadt affvanintagne Hemmål till Herr Grevernöraren i Länet, som sedermera remitterat ären- gäll:</p>
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The personal name NERs identified are:

Adam Lepistö	Correct
Johan Wilhelm Typén	Incorrectly transcribed surname, correct surname is Nygren
Johan Thomasson Hynttinen	Incorrectly transcribed surname, correct surname is Mynttinen
Mårten Hårtersson Hy	Incorrectly transcribed name, correct patronymic is Mårtensson and surname is truncated, correct surname is Hyryläinen
JuliaTyp	Incorrectly transcribed name, correct name is Julius Nygren
Henrik Gabriel Savenius	Correct
Adam Sigfridsson	Correct, however, surname is missed and not connected
Anders Mattsson Nikkinen	Correct

GabSavenius

First name is missing and second name is connected to surname incorrectly, surname is transcribed correctly